

101112135 - IDERHA

Integration of heterogeneous Data and Evidence towards Regulatory and HTA Acceptance

WP7 – Exploitation, communication and dissemination

D7.2 Description of Communication and dissemination tools

Lead contributor	3-LYG
Other contributors	18-PMS, 20-LH, 2-JJM, 1-FHI

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Due date	30-09-2023
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Dissemination level	PU

Document History

Version	Date	Description
V0.1	31/7/23	Draft
V0.2	13/9/23	Amended after consultation
V0.3	18/9/23	Amended after consultation
V1.0	19/9/23	Submitted to PMO for review, shared with WP7 members
V1.1	27/9/23	Amended and submitted to PMO

Executive Summary

The items listed in this deliverable are an overview of all current and near-future tools that contribute to our three communication fundamentals: build the team, share the progress, be part of the conversation. More information on the overall strategy can be found in the CDE plan (D7.1).

In each activity and tool described below, we discuss how each will contribute to the success of IDERHA for both internal and external communications. Tools that are not explicitly described in the DoA are to be considered optional.

Introduction

The strategy in the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation plan (CDE; deliverable D7.1) is implemented through a set of communication tools and activities, which are described in this deliverable. The overall strategy is based on three communication fundamentals – build the team, share the progress, be part of the conversation – and each tool and activity contributes to one or more of these fundamentals:

Any activity listed as 'Permitted Communications' in the Communication Guidelines (Appendix 6) of the Coalition Agreement (CA) can be undertaken.

WP7 – Exploitation, communication and dissemination

D7.2 Description of communication and dissemination tools

Co-funded by
the European Union

Description of Communication and Dissemination Tools

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Internal Communications

build | inform | share | advise

Sharepoint

Besides being an internal document exchange platform, SharePoint provides an easy to maintain, basic project homepage where we can publish news items as well as general information for IDERHA participants.

Microsoft 365 Zoeken op deze site

IDERHA Toegang tot site

Delen

Start

- Documenten
- Meetings
- Project Members
- Deliverables Tracker
- Prullenbak

Welcome to IDERHA SharePoint

Nieuws [Alles weergeven](#)

+ Toevoegen

IDERHA Zotero Library is Live

Dear IDERHA consortium members,...

Nebo Savic | Lygature 4 dagen geleden 6 weergaven

IDERHA on LinkedIn: Information Package Nominations IDAGC

Call for Integrated Data Access Governan...
Duyndam, Alexander (Lygature) 4 dagen geleden 5 weergaven

IDERHA communication toolbox is steadily increasing

Over the past months, WP7 has been...
Erwin Boutsma | Lygature 21 augustus 25 weergaven

ESMO Congress 2023

Dear IDERHA partners, The ESMO congre...
George Kolostoumpis 21 augustus 19 weergaven

IDERHA Calendar

Literat... [Alles weergeven](#)

and events of interest

... [Alle documenten](#)

Naam

IDERHA
integrating health data

IDERHA

IDERHA Internal Newsletter | August 2023

Dear IDERHA participants, this is our first internal newsletter: news relevant to the consortium, important dates about upcoming events, etc. All with the purpose of building our community of people working towards a common goal.

Next to this internal newsletter, we plan on sending out a quarterly external newsletter later on. This newsletter is aimed at the outside world: what do we do, why is it relevant, and how do we impact patient's lives in the EU?

If you feel anything is missing or if you have ideas on how to proceed, please feel free to send us an e-mail: communications@iderha.org

[IDERHA communication toolbox is steadily increasing](#)

Over the past months, WP7 has been working on communication materials for the consortium. Currently, we have the following materials ready: The IDERHA corporate slide deck (will be updated regularly) IDERHA PowerPoint slide templates for your own pr...

Internal Newsletter

Sharepoint enables us to quickly and easily compile a list of news items and other messages that needs to be shared among IDERHA partners. This overview, essentially an internal newsletter, is then pushed every other month via e-mail to all participants.

Mailing Lists

PMO set up several mailing lists, making internal e-mail communication faster and easier.

Slack

As a quick, group-based communication tool, Slack was implemented and encouraged to use for quick, cross-work package communication.

External Communications

strategy | marketing | exploitation | partnerships

Visual Identity

A set of colors, logos, images, graphics, icons, slide deck templates and more were made available to the consortium members early in the project. This will enable them to communicate in a professional and consistent way, both internally as well as externally.

Website

A project website integrates all information on the project itself and the individual project bodies, providing general information and presenting progress and results in news items. Functionality for registration modules for newsletters and webinars is built in. We use privacy-friendly website analytics (Matomo) to monitor the use of the website. During the project, the website will be expanded and updated regularly.

www.iderha.org

IDERHA
integrating health data

About | Partners | Outreach | Contact |
Boards & Councils | Newsroom

Welcome to IDERHA

Improving clinical decision-making and enhancing patient access to health innovations through better use of health data.

IDERHA's workshop series kickstarts with patients leading the way.
15 September 2023 →

Call for Integrated Data Access Governance Council Member Nominations
6 September 2023 →

First IDERHA 'hackathon' produces basic IDERHA architecture
2 August 2023 →

Events

Events and scientific conferences will be a key part of IDERHA to adhere to its transparency principles. Internally and externally aimed events are an excellent way to connect with stakeholders, the general public, and stimulate cross-work package collaboration. Currently, we aim to organize an annual Public Forum at the same time as the General Meeting of the consortium. Content and a program will be developed.

Q&As

Based on the trend analysis in this CDE plan, we aim to provide a set of Q&As for the spokespersons of IDERHA. This will enable the consortium and its key players to quickly respond to questions or concerns that might arise among the general public.

Scientific Publications

The PMO (Project Management Office) has developed a workflow to improve the approval process before the publication to make sure it follows the requirements/restrictions in the GA.

Animations

To make complex issues clearer, we plan to use animations in situations where the return-on-investment is high enough.

LinkedIn

The most effective social media channel for professional outreach is LinkedIn. It is widely known to be a valuable tool to connect with professionals in the life sciences & healthcare field. The aim of our IDERHA corporate page is to stimulate participants to add IDERHA as an additional occupation to increase the visibility of IDERHA. With posts on LinkedIn, we can echo our news items from the website. In the future we could consider starting a dialogue. This might require close monitoring and the development of a Q&A.

www.linkedin.com/company/iderha

X (formerly named Twitter)

Despite recent changes and controversies, micro-blogging tool X is still a valuable channel to disseminate our activities to the outside world. Its key value is that X connects journalists, policy makers and scientists around current topics. However, since the sentiment has soured as X's content moderation has declined, leaving more room for extremist views and hate, we will closely monitor the developments around X. Currently, the functionality of IDERHA's X channel is in place.

www.x.com/iderha_2023

The screenshot displays the X profile for IDERHA (@IDERHA_2023). The profile header includes the IDERHA logo, the tagline 'integrating health data', and a bio: 'IHI-project to improve clinical decision-making and enhance patient access to health innovations through better use of health data.' The profile also shows location (Utrecht, The Netherlands), website (iderha.org), and creation date (Lid sinds juni 2023). There are 76 followers and 54 following. The main content area shows a post from Lotte Groth Jensen (@grothjensen) retweeted by IDERHA. The post text reads: 'You should consider joining us in the IDAGC if you are interested in the use of European health data for research and regulatory processes. In @DKFACT we think this is really important work.' The post has 1 retweet and 4 likes. The IDERHA profile picture is a circular logo with four colored quadrants (grey, blue, green, purple).

Whitepapers

We will provide communications support to publish whitepapers and position papers, sharing insights from the consortium to the broader community.

External Newsletter

We will develop a digital quarterly magazine to inform our stakeholders in the innovation ecosystem. A template will be developed where we can introduce the members of the consortium to the general public, share results and insights and articles/interviews about current topics around IDERHA, etc.

Young Investors Program

We want to find ways to connect junior researchers and give them a presence in IDERHA events and webinars. Such a program strengthens the connections between junior researchers and promotes collaboration.

PRESS RELEASE

Philip Gribbon: "IDERHA is a pioneering project focussed on creating health care solutions that integrate diverse health data, to bring improved care and treatments for patients"

Integrating Health Data across Europe to aid Clinical Decision-making for Lung Cancer Patients

The newly formed [IDERHA](#) consortium, consisting of academia, industry, health authorities, clinicians, and patient representatives, addresses the obstacles in accessing, integrating & analysing health data to maximize their value for patient care and research. Focusing on lung cancer, IDERHA wants to use complex digital health data to improve patient health outcomes by enabling more personalized care.

14 June 2023 – Today a consortium of public and private entities announced the official launch of [IDERHA](#) (Integration of heterogenous Data and Evidence towards Regulatory & HTA Acceptance). The consortium aims to propel health care innovation in Europe by addressing the key obstacles to achieve appropriate access, sharing, use and reuse of digital healthcare data. IDERHA will, therefore, develop the first pan-European health data space, and through policy recommendations drive health data access and the acceptability of heterogeneous health research results for regulatory and Health Technology Assessment decision-making. The initiative will focus on lung cancer, one of the key priorities of the [Europe Beating Cancer](#) and which is responsible for [20% of cancer-related deaths in Europe](#).

IDERHA is one of the first research projects funded through the [Innovative Health Initiative \(IHI\)](#), a public-private partnership (PPP) between the European Union and the European life science industries that supports transformative research and innovation.

Press Releases

We will use press releases to inform international media about major project results. We liaison with partners to map media relations available within the consortium to be able pitch results to connected journalists.

Corporate Slide-deck

We have developed a PowerPoint slide-deck with general information about the IDERHA project, partners, its environment, work packages, boards, funders, etc. The slide deck is a living document that will continuously be updated as the project progresses.

Key Facts

- **Timeline:** 1 April 2023
- **Partners:** 32 public and private
- **Budget:** € 42.7 million
- **Website:** www.iderha.org
- **LinkedIn:** www.linkedin.com/company/iderha
- **X (formerly Twitter):** x.com/iderha_2023
- **Contact address:** communications@iderha.org
- **IHI grant number:** 101112135

Partner Partners from 10 Countries in Europe, -EU support

Research & public

industry & SME

associated

affiliated

Logos of partner organizations including: ERS, hygia so, NICE, PHILIPS, Takeda, SANOFI, labcorp, Roche, EPF, lygature, IIS La Fe, ASKLEPIOS, VTT, and others.

GitHub

We use GitHub as a platform and cloud-based service for software development and version control using Git, allowing developers to store and manage their code. GitHub has been a subsidiary of Microsoft since 2018. IDERHA intends to share code within the open science ambitions.

Zenodo

We use Zenodo as a general-purpose, open repository developed under the European OpenAIRE program and operated by CERN. It allows researchers to deposit research papers, data sets, research software, reports, and any other research-related digital artefacts. For each submission, a persistent digital object identifier (DOI) is minted, which makes the stored items easily citable. We will use Zenodo to publish relevant results and other information that might be helpful for other PPPs.

Video

We will claim an IDERHA channel on the video platform YouTube. For example, the short personal videos recorded during the kick-off in Berlin will be published there when edited. Recording of external events will also be published on YouTube, as long as we comply with the CDA. It can also be a platform for self-produced content such as animations.

Webinars

Outreach activities to inform the general public as well as specific stakeholders are a key part of IDERHA. Several work packages have either planned or shown interest in organizing webinars around relevant topics, including patient engagement and regulatory acceptance. We will facilitate and provide communication support where needed.

Infographics

Within the project, we develop and use graphic representations of governance structures, goals, pipelines, etc as much as possible. It is an efficient and visually appealing way to share information.

Media Monitoring

Through the service provider Meltwater, we have installed a media monitor tool. Meltwater enables us to follow the conversation online and offline for issues relevant to IDERHA. Currently, we have a limited scope using key words 'IDERHA' and the names of the project coordinators. We aim to extend this in the future.

EU-owned Dissemination Channels

We aim to map all EU dissemination channels (i.e., CORDIS, Horizon Magazine, IHI newsletters, IHI website, etc.) and connect with those responsible for the editorial content. This will make our outreach efforts more efficient.

Working Group 'IHI Data Projects Communication'

As several past, current and future IMI and IHI projects (i.e., BY-COVID, EOSC4Cancer, EHDEN, OSCAR) are aimed at improving the use of data in the healthcare system, we aim to reach out to these projects to share best practices in communication, dissemination and exploitation.

Leaflet

In collaboration with the PMO and MT, we developed a leaflet to briefly describe the project and its key information (i.e. objectives, governance, partners, values). The flyer can be distributed during external events and face-to-face meetings, both digitally and as a hard copy. It can be found on Zenodo under the following DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.8366116](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8366116)

IDERHA
integrating health data

IDERHA is an open platform designed to enable connectivity, access, sharing, use and reuse of digital health data. Our policy recommendations will enhance regulatory and HTA decision making, facilitating access to digital health innovations for patients and health care professionals.

HTA & Regulatory Acceptance Policy

Standards & Data Management

Public Health Management

Oncology & Lung Cancer

AI/ML Development

Patient-related Outcomes

Governance
Standards, Ethics, Legal

Data formats
OMOP, FHIR, DICOM, XML, ...

Transforming data into better healthcare
In recent years, there has been an exponential growth in the generation of data that could be harnessed for use in healthcare delivery and research. These data include datasets generated by digital technologies, patient reported outcome and experience measures, and results from clinical trials and routine clinical care. However, assessing, integrating and analysing these data to maximize their value for patient care and research is extremely challenging.

IDERHA (Integration of heterogeneous Data and Evidence towards Regulatory & HTA Acceptance)
The project aims to create a scalable platform for the seamless integration or linkage of diverse data to support healthcare professionals, patients, and researchers with new capabilities to improve patient outcomes. The new platform will be based on the development of common standards and practices - reducing current disconnected information silos. This enables more personalised health care along the patient's journey via data-driven tools and solutions. The consortium will, therefore, develop the first pan-European health data space, and through policy recommendations drive health data access and the acceptability of heterogeneous health research results for regulatory and Health Technology Assessment decision-making.

Lung cancer as EU's key priority
IDERHA will focus on lung cancer, which is responsible for 20% of cancer-related deaths in Europe and one of the key priorities of the Europe Beating Cancer program.

The project will link and analyse diverse data of a lung cancer patient's journey from early screening of citizens at risk, to development of lung cancer, to remote monitoring of late-stage patients to enable better care in an at home setting. Ultimately, the platform and policy recommendations will be disease independent.

Accelerate policy development
To enable patients and health care providers to benefit from novel health solutions, IDERHA also seeks to accelerate policy development. Informed by patient needs, we will develop consensus recommendations for fully compliant health data access and sharing, as well as for the acceptability of heterogeneous health research results for regulatory and HTA decision-making. This may lead to a framework for data governance that can be used as a model globally.

'IDERHA is a pioneering project focussed on creating health care solutions that integrate diverse health data, to bring improved care and treatments for patients.'

KEY FACTS

IDERHA leadership & management:
IDERHA is led by the Fraunhofer Institute for Translational Medicine and Pharmacology ITMP and Johnson & Johnson Medical GmbH, part of Johnson & Johnson MedTech. The management team consists of Dr. Philip Gibbon (Fraunhofer ITMP) and Dr. Christian Muehlenryck MD (Johnson & Johnson MEDICAL GmbH).

Consortium partners:
33 academic, clinical, medtech, pharmaceutical, IT and patient advocacy organizations as well as public authorities from across the EU and the world.

Funding:
IDERHA is among the first projects funded through the EU Innovative Health Initiative (IHI), a public private partnership (PPP) between the EU and the European life science industries. IDERHA's total budget is € 42.7 mln (plus contributions from Associated Partners from Switzerland and the UK).

Duration:
IDERHA will run for 3 years, from 1 April 2023 - 31 March 2026.

More information:
info@iderha.org